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RELATIVE EFFECTIVENESS OF DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY ON MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS (SSII) IN CALABAR EDUCATION ZONE: A MEANS OF ACHIEVING SDGs IN NIGERIA

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&
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Abstract

The place of Mathematics in fostering a sustainably developed society is global and critical in the 21st century. Incidentally, the development goals and targets which underlie the emerged global UNN – induced programmes; the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and now its offshoot, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have as one of their roots in the quest for a technologically based society where citizens are encouraged to be innovative and creative, to create wealth through productive employment and reduced poverty. Effectiveness in the strategies for handling Mathematics can be a fundamental tool in the realization of goals and programmes of development in Nigeria. This study investigated the relative effectiveness of differentiated instructional strategy on senior secondary school students' academic achievement in mathematics in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. The study sought to provide answer to one research question and test one null hypothesis formulated to guide the study. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research using pretest and post-test control group design involving intact classes. A total sample of 60 (30 male and 30 female) students were used for the study. Purposive multi-stage random sampling technique was utilized. The study made use of two instruments. The first was non-cognitive which involved the design of three instructional packages and the second was a Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) made up of 25 essay type questions designed specifically to measure the achievement of students in some units of instruction in Mathematics. Data collected were subjected to statistical analysis using independent t-test. The findings of the study show the following results: (i) instructional strategy of students' academic achievement in mathematics; (ii) there is a significant interaction effect of differentiated instructional strategy. Recommendations were drawn based on findings.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Differentiated instructional strategy, Mathematics Achievement, Senior Secondary, Sustainable Development Goals.

Introduction

Mathematics probably started with the early man's attempt to keep tract of his belongings. For example, he would want to know how many arrowheads he had, how many wives he had, how many people there were in his household after children had been born and older members had died. He probably even wanted to know how many chicken he now had after the last hatching. This humble beginning of Mathematics then gave rise to the counting of numbers, which are basic to Mathematics concept development (Enukoha, 2010). In

African traditional societies, many people told time by the number of cockcrows, length was measured by the use of foot and hand span. (Fennema& Sherman, 2001).

In the modern societies, Mathematics continues to play important role in our daily activities. There is virtually no profession in which Mathematics does not play some part. The invention of pocket scientific calculator and computer has simplified basic mathematical processes for the common user. This invention has also introduced incredible

speed, accuracy and elegance into human activity (Obo, 2005) and daily problem solving.

Literature has found that despite the ubiquitous use of Mathematics in all our daily activities, many children and sometimes adults continue to fear, dislike and even hate the formal study of mathematics. A number of factors are responsible for this situation. Akinsola, (2004) noted that many teachers at the primary and secondary school level are not properly equipped to teach mathematics. The author noted also that some of the teachers teach it not because they have adequate training and sound knowledge of the subject, or because they enjoy it, but because they are compelled by their head teachers or principals to teach it in the absence of competent hands.

As Mathematics and Maths related tutors, the researchers have encountered a lot of the above issues in schools and classroom and these have become a source of inspiration to explore how differentiated instructional strategies might influence students' achievement in Mathematics. In some secondary schools, some teachers who are not graduates of Mathematics have been observed to voluntarily accept to teach it so as to earn additional income through private lessons since Mathematics is a compulsory subject in schools. Consequently, the teaching is done poorly and with nonchalance. Similarly, many teachers in primary and junior secondary schools are not able to move Mathematics from the theoretical to concrete level for students. As a result, Mathematics lessons do not show any connection to students' life experiences and their environment. Most of the lessons taught remain at the abstract level and involve mere manipulation of numbers, symbols and relations (Copper, 1994).

National Policy on Education (FRN, 2004) has made it a policy that Mathematics be made an essential subject in all schools in Nigeria. That was done in an effort to attain a meaningful national development and technological breakthrough through Mathematics at all levels of education. This inadequate background in Mathematics rather makes these teachers of Mathematics in primary and junior secondary schools impatient

with students, which in turn generates fear among the students and frustration among the teachers. This vicious cycle may be as a result of teachers who do not understand the structure, concept formation and communication in Mathematics (Armstrong & Prince, 2005).

Today, Mathematics continues to gain popularity all over the globe due to its wide application in almost all fields of human endeavour including military, recreation, engineering, catering, and book keeping, to mention a few. In the most recent years, Mathematics has also found considerable application in the social sciences especially those that deal with the prediction of human behavior. It is becoming conventional that courses like economics, business, psychology, sociology and political science require college calculus, matrix and linear algebra, analytical and plane geometry, differential calculus etc. The developments have considerable implication for secondary school curriculum (Bolaji, 2000). It is important to note that in spite of the great position that Mathematics occupies in our lives and its great role in the scientific and technological advancement worldwide, it not only continues to be a challenge to students but its standard in overall has been deplorable and miserable (Akpan, 1989).

In line with the development goals or targets of different times, all levels of government in Nigeria (local, state and federal) have instituted educational programs at all levels of schooling ranging from free distribution of Mathematics texts, training of Mathematics educators, scholarships to all best achieving students in both secondary and tertiary levels, among others. All these are meant to encourage and inspire the pursuit of the study of Mathematics or related areas in young learners who would be nation builders of the future. (Okubunkwo, 1997). According to Erukoha (2010), today, many Nigerian universities and polytechnics must organize remedial and preliminary learning environments focused on strengthening the foundation for mathematical skills so as to bridge the gap which both tutors and students

encounter in their course of teaching, and learning mathematics and compete favourably in the global arena.

The problem of low achievement by students in Mathematics is like a cankerworm that is eating deeper by the day into Nigeria's educational system and is a major hindrance to the technological advancement of the country. Students have responded to this situation in a negative way. Rather than investing energy and time in studying, students direct most of their efforts at looking for ways to cheat in order to pass Mathematics examinations. This is indicated by the high rate of examination malpractice incidents observed at all stages of learning in Nigeria education (Idika, 2004; Mofinews, 2006). Some students abstain completely from Mathematics classes and perceive attending classes as waste of time. The situation is so deplorable that school principals and teachers can no longer handle or control truant students from Mathematics classes, and all efforts to bring these students to see the need to study Mathematics has proved abortive (Basse, 2002). This wrong impression has been transferred to the younger students in the junior classes. This is indicated by the rate at which the junior secondary school students get involved in examination malpractices especially in mathematics. The situation has been aggravated by lack of good instructional strategies or approaches, qualified and committed teachers in both junior and senior secondary schools.

In Nigeria, a number of steps have been taken to arrest this ugly situation. Different governments have provided incentives such as scholarships for both teachers and students studying Mathematics and the sciences in the universities. Cross River State Government for instance published her 2006 maiden scholarship awards to science students and has since regularly done so to encourage students. Others include payment of Mathematics teacher's allowances, in-service training, workshops, etc. Some non-governmental bodies have also contributed immensely through organization of their annual conferences, seminars, and workshops towards improvement of the teaching of Mathematics in

schools. STAN held her 2006 annual conference in Calabar between (13th-19th Aug, 2006) for science, technology and Mathematics teachers; the most recent conference organized by STAN in Calabar was 2015.

The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2008) has made Mathematics compulsory subject of junior and senior secondary school curriculum. This importance accorded Mathematics in the school curriculum reflects accurately the recognition of the vital roles it plays in the world at large, especially when the wide goals of secondary education within our national objectives are aimed at preparing students for higher education (FRN, 2008) which specifically equip students' to live functionally in this era of science and technology.

For the method of teaching and learning of Mathematics to be more efficient and for students to learn while teaching is going on, the psychological factors such as age, family background, parents' perception of the learners involved have to be put into consideration. The students involved also need to be incorporated into the teaching method, so as to get them functional in the classroom teaching procedure. There is need for the adoption of some learner-centered teaching strategies such as problem solving and concept mapping which could enhance understanding of mathematical concepts and problems and thus improve their academic performance. However, to this end, a vital objective in teaching mathematics is to improve problem solving abilities of students (Abimbade, 1997). The development of the ability to recognize problems and to solve them in relation to mathematical knowledge has been widely recognized as one of the objectives of the secondary school Mathematics (Abimbade, 1997). But certain educational practices such as rote learning, teachers desire to provide conclusion and answers, excessive use of word problem and problems may not be appropriate for the students level of maturation and experience which tend to hamper optimum development of the understanding of Mathematics and which often lead to failure in the subject (Obilor, 2011).

In practice, emphasis is placed on teachers teaching activities rather than the learners learning. A case has been made that the program of instruction has tended to over-emphasize manipulative aspect of Mathematics with entirely negligible concentration being given to the conceptual aspects of the subject (Obilor, 2011). Therefore, the program of instruction should permit students to explore conjectural experiment and improve their skills so that they become effectively occupied in doing Mathematics through problem solving, problem posing and classroom discourse (Enukoha, 2004).

Education deals with persons, society, things and ideas. This statement can be extended by saying that education is concerned with individuals, their social environment and their spiritual environment. According to Joan (1977) without effective teaching, there is no effective learning. In teaching methods, techniques and strategies are used. They vary in effectiveness – some methods are better than others in terms of accomplishing desired objectives. Effective teaching is based on sound methods. Mathematics being one of the core school subjects requires differentiated or a variety of teaching methods aimed at promoting agility, innovation and creativity for sustainable development of the individual learner and the society. Previous investigations have shown a significant relationship between teaching methods and academic achievement.

Statement of the problems

The Nigerian National Policy on Education (FRN, 2004) has made mathematics a requisite subject for junior and senior secondary school curriculum. It reflects the recognition of the unique roles it plays in meeting the science and technology challenges of the global market. Again, considering the broad goals of secondary education in our National Policy on Education which is the preparation for higher education and specifically equipping learners to function in this new era of science and technology; it is clear that knowledge of Mathematics is very necessary for the attainment of these goals. The inability of students to acquire this required

knowledge in Mathematics is one of the major problems in studying secondary school mathematics.

Personality factors, teacher's knowledge of subject matter, class-size management, the instructional strategies (approaches) adopted in imparting knowledge by the teacher, gender and age of the students may be responsible for the poor academic achievement of students. These may be responsible for the advocacy of different teaching approaches by different theorists. Is there any relative effect of the collaborative guided instructional strategies on students' achievement in senior secondary school mathematics?

The major purpose of this study was to investigate relative effectiveness of differentiated instructional strategy which involved collaborative guided method of teaching Mathematics in our secondary schools on students' academic achievements in the subject. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Identify the most effective strategy in respect to differentiated instructional strategy on students' Mathematics achievement when taught with collaborative guided strategy.
2. Assess the joint effect of teaching strategies.

Research question

To what extent does differentiated instructional strategy influence students' academic achievement in Mathematics?

Research hypothesis

There is no significant interaction effect of differentiated instructional strategy on students' academic achievement in Mathematics.

Methodology

This is a quasi-experimental research using pre-test and post-test control groups design involving intact classes. This design was adopted because was not possible to have an accurate randomization of subjects. Moreso, this design was chosen because it controls the internal validity threat of the initial group equivalence and researcher selection bias, since

there is no randomization of the subjects into groups. The intact classes were already organized into classes in order not to destabilize school activities, classroom schedule and sitting arrangement in the sampled schools so selected. The study used two instruments. The first was non-cognitive which involved the design of three instructional strategies or packages. Each strategy was based on the selected instructional approach; discussion, problem solving and collaborative guided. The other instrument for this study was a Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) that was made up of 25 essay type questions designed specifically to measure the achievement of students in some units of instruction in mathematics. The test was administered on the students after the experiment with the instructional strategies. The data were collected during the beginning

of third-term of the academic session. The study lasted for a period of two weeks for the experiment and one week for the test. First week of experiment was characterized by 90 minutes of double period of Mathematics instructions and sometimes single period of Mathematics class. The experimental groups were treated with discussion, problem-solving, and collaborative guided method respectively, while the control groups were supervised by the researchers to ensure that they do not indulge in discussing or copying which will not help the researchers to get the actual results. The test was administered after the experiment and treatment group have completed instruction on some units in Mathematics which consist of number and numeration, simultaneous equation, trigonometry and probability.

Result

Independent t-test analysis of the interactive effects of differentiated instructional strategy on male and female students' academic attainment in mathematics

Instructional strategy	Sex	N	$\bar{x}$	SD	t.
Discussion	Female	30	30.61	5.476	2.301*
	Male	30	28.23	5.299	
Problem solving	Female	30	29.46	5.535	0.098
	Male	30	29.58	6.114	
Collaborative	Female	30	29.94	5.335	3.322*
	Male	30	33.48	5.579	

Significant at 0.05 levels; $df = 58$; critical $t = 1.980$.

Discussion of findings

From the hypothesis, the findings revealed that there were meaningful effects ($F = 13.455$; $p < 0.05$; $df 2.58$). This happens since the respondents were treated differently with different instructional strategies and from the result it was believed that students can learn adequately if teaching strategies were used properly as the case may be. "Without effective teaching there is no effective learning" Joan (1997). In treating strategies or methods, techniques are used, that the effectiveness of some methods are better than others in terms of

accomplishing desired objectives and that effective teaching is based on sound methods. Since Mathematics has been one of the core school subjects that requires a variety of teaching strategies, from previous investigations we have seen a meaningful relationship between teaching strategies and academic achievement in mathematics.

On the other hand, Udoh (1991), observed that methods should be organized orderly and systematically in a way to achieve a given objective. Stressing further, instructional approach is how to deliver a

lesson in order to achieve a desired result. To him, the importance of method is borne out of the fact that there can be no form of teaching without the use of some kind of strategy or method, but only the use of appropriate strategies in a given situation will achieve the desired results.

Further, the result, emphasized that "teachers perception of student errors not only influence the approach of instructions, but, it also affected the selection of content and activities as well as guiding and corrections procedure" Novak (2001). In line with the results of the study, Babalola (2000) studied the relationship between scientific inquiry process and collaborative process in connection with students' achievement in Mathematics. The study revealed a significantly superior achievement for collaborative students. In the same vein, Babalola (2000) suggested that it would seem reasonable and prudent to encourage students with collaborative strategy of learning in Nigeria secondary schools for the achievement of developmental targets in education.

Also, the present study on the "effect of differentiated instructional strategy on students' academic achievement in Mathematics" is in agreement with the study of Shuaibu and Ogunsola (2000) who examined the achievement of Mathematics students using heath's type of instrument. They were interested in finding out whether there is a relationship between students achievement on their training method. Their results along side that of Idaka, Akubuiro and Umohong (2012) on "Blended Cooperative/Technology Interactive Strategy with Conventional Lecture Technique and its Impacts on Students' Learning Outcomes Inorganic Chemistry" indicated that Nigerian students showed high achievement to collaborative teaching strategy. The study also confirmed the study of Vaughn, Elbaum. In another study, the social outcome for students in collaborative classroom obtained a positive outcome. In the study the sample consisted 185 six grade students, distributed between low achievement, average achievement and high achievement. The participants were distributed between two

different settings; co-teaching and collaborative teaching setting. According to the result, the students on the collaborative teaching setting demonstrated a more positive outcome than their peers on the co-teaching setting. Further, it was demonstrated that there was an increase in the number of reciprocal friendship formed. The superiority of collaborative guided strategy over other strategies of teaching enhanced performance in mathematics. This is because teacher-to-students and student-to-student communication is very effective and functional. Moreso, some students reason and think much faster than some of their mates in the class and this also stimulates students' interest in a group work which is and opens freely to every sampled respondent in the school.

Conclusion

On the basis of the findings of this study, it was seen that:

- (1) Instructional strategy applied by a teacher is a factor affecting students' academic achievement in mathematics.
- (2) It was also seen that students who were taught Mathematics by using discussion and collaborative guided strategy do better than those ones taught by problem solving. From the results of the analysis carried out, it showed significantly that collaborative guided was greater than discussion and discussion show greater value than problem solving which can be shown mathematically as collaborative guided > discussion > problem solving.

Recommendation

On the basis of this, it was recommended that a major strategy to improve students Mathematics performance is adoption of differentiated approach to the teaching of the subject. In this way, this can enhance creative and innovative skills of students and ultimately promote sustainability.

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